

Designing Service Level Agreements and Information Technology Service Level Management Process Standards based on the ISO 20000 and ITIL V3 2011: Case Study of PT XYZ

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Abstract—The development of technology today is very fast and has changed companies' perspective and strategic plans. The knowledge of information technology has begun to reach the strategic level, but there are still many companies that have not been able to map the development of information technology from its strategic level. PT XYZ is a customer relationship management-based company that provides several services to meet its business needs. Some of these services have problems regarding their service capabilities. Many businesspeople question whether the IT division is able to provide everything needed by the business and whether the IT division in accordance with the agreement, with this problem a service level agreement document will be made that is in line with the business requirements expected by the board of directors of PT XYZ. However, some of these problems have measures that have never been defined before, so they cannot produce something that can be measured and assessed. This study seeks to develop service level agreements that are in accordance with formal standards that are not yet available at PT XYZ using the ISO 20000 standard and the 2011 ITIL V3 framework and develop measures that can be measured and assessed. This service level agreement will contain 19 parts, each of which will be customized based on the characteristics of the service and the company

Keywords: *Service Level Agreement; Service Level Management; ISO 20000; ITIL V3 2011*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology today is very fast and has changed companies' perspective and strategic plans. The knowledge of information technology has begun to reach the strategic level, but there are still many companies that have not been able to map the development of information

technology from its strategic level. PT XYZ is a customer relationship management-based company.

PT XYZ has a vision to become a major CRM company that helps clients achieve their business goals in the continuously changing consumer space by providing data-driven, actionable, and accountable solutions. Problems that arise in PT XYZ focus on service capabilities provided by the IT division are not yet optimal.

Their services problems start from the unclear planning stage of IT development services to the many problems that arise in IT services that has gone live, causing clients' trust to decrease. Based on the initial analysis with the IT Head, the problems to be discussed are problems coming from the organization and management domain, namely the absence of a formal management process and the absence of a service level agreement.

From the problems that arise on the surface, the research question to be solved in this study is what are the contents of the service level agreement that suits the needs of PT XYZ? How are IT service level management standards implemented so that they can meet the needs of PT XYZ? The aim of this research is to make PT XYZ's IT service level agreement in accordance with the results of the implementation of ISO 20000 and ITIL V3 2011 and to make PT XYZ IT service level management standards using ITIL V3 2011 based on the results of using ISO 20000.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Measuring the quality of IT services is more difficult than measuring the quality of goods. This is because IT services are intangible and unclear (indistinct obstruct). Quality of service is a measure of how a service can provide what customers expect. Service information data is a de facto standard in defining services. Defining IT services is the first step in the process of Service Portfolio Management (SPM), Business Service Management (BSM), Service Level

Management (SLM) and Information Technology Service Management (ITSM). [1]

Service information data defines two types of services, namely services used by customers or Customer Facing Services (CFS) and services that support services used by customers but not visible to customers or Resource Facing Services (RFS). RFS is used to build CFS. Some steps to determine services that are included in CFS, RFS and resources are as follows: [2]

1. Select company products and identify the services that support them.
2. Make a list of IT services that support the product.
3. Mark the CFS or RFS.
4. Map the CFS and RFS.
5. Identify Resources that support RFS.

Figure 1 describes the relationship between CFS, RFS, and resources with the products or services that the company has:

Figure 1. The Relationship between CFS, RFS, and Resources.

Information Technology Service Management is a set of organizational specific capabilities to deliver value to customers and businesses in the form of IT services. The aim of Information Technology Service Management is to provide the quality and level of service needed by businesses and to continually improve the quality of services provided to customers so that they can reduce costs effectively (Rudd, 2007). One of the main capabilities needed in the service management process is the ability to measure all service quality, effectiveness, and efficiency of the process. [3]

This research will focus on one of the ISO 20000 processes, namely the Service Delivery Process in which there is a Service Level Management (SLM) sub-process. This management aims to establish, agree, record, and manage service levels.

ITIL is a best practice related to Information Technology Service Management. The 2011 ITIL V3 life cycle is based on the service management concept that is tied to service and value. The service life cycle consists of five stages, the initial stage in the service life cycle starts with the initial definition and analysis of the business demand on service strategy and

service design, after that, migrating into an active environment in service transition (Service Transition), up to the active process and improvement in service operations and continuity of service improvement (Continual Service Improvement). [4]

Each stage has a direct impact on service performance. In essence, services are expected to provide structure, stability, and strength for service management capabilities with durable principles, methods, and equipment's. The IT service life cycle according to ITIL V3 2011 is as follows [4]:

Figure 2. IT Service Life Cycle according to ITIL V3 2011

Service Level Management in ITIL V3 2011 is conducting negotiation, approval, and documentation activities to ensure the existence of IT service targets with business representatives and then oversee and produce reports on the ability of service providers to provide a level of service in accordance with the agreement. The objectives of the SLM process are as follows [5]:

1. To ensure that the agreed level of IT services for all IT services activities and future IT services are given and agreed targets are achieved.
2. To ensure that all operational services and service performance are measured consistently, professionally throughout the organization, and that the produced services and reports meet the business and customer needs.
3. To establish, document, approve, monitor, measure, report and review the level of available IT services.
4. To provide and improve communication links between business and customers.
5. To ensure that the targets are specific and measurable to be developed on all IT services.
6. To ensure that IT and customers have clear and unambiguous expectations regarding the communicated level of service.
7. To ensure proactive measures to increase the level of service provided have been implemented at any cost structure.

The parts that must be included in the SLA document are service descriptions, service scope, service time, service availability, service reliability, customer support, contactable personnel and escalation, service performance, batch

turnaround times, functions, change management, service continuity, security, printing, responsibility, charging, reporting services and evaluation processes, terms, and amendments sheet. [5]

Amongst the challenges IT faces is determining metrics that must be measured in a part that has been previously defined. Metrics will aim to help calculation in a section so that it can know how much value is obtained in that section, and how it performs. A high value or low will provide a broad view for management so the management can make decisions for the future. According to Randy A. Steinberg, IT metrics have several categories, namely operational, key performance indicators, tolerance, critical success factors, dashboards, and reports. These metrics have the following relationships [6]:

Figure 3. Relationships between metrics

Some of the previous research that took the same theme with this research were as follows:

Tabel 1. Differences between this Research with some Previous Research

Differences	Previous Research			Al Farozi (2013)
	Hammi (2009)	Akmal (2011)	Utama (2013)	
Standard	ISO 20000	ISO 20000, ISO 27001	-	ISO 20000
Framework	ITIL V2	COBIT 4.1	ITIL V3 2011	ITIL V3 2011
Research Object	Educational Institution	PT Bhandha Ghara Reksa	Pusat Grosir Cililitan	PT XYZ
Final Result	Service Management Implementation Plan	Policy	Service Management Mechanism	Service Level Agreement

Information technology service management has two theories, one ISO 20000 standard and one ITIL V3 2011 framework. In ISO 20000 it has a cycle called PDCA, which is the Deming cycle. In the PDCA Cycle in ISO 20000 there is a Service Level Management process. The Service Level Management process has information technology service management standards regarding Service Level Management. The ITIL V3 2011 framework has a Service Design section in which there is a Service Level Management process.

The ITIL V3 Service Level Management 2011 has sections on service level agreements that can be used for the making of service level agreements. In each part of the service level agreement, there are quantifiable metrics. Each metric has a target and tolerance that has been agreed upon. These metrics have calculations that can be used for the making of service level agreements. The current condition of the company supports the arrangement of service level agreements so that it can be said that the company currently has a service level agreement. The above theoretical framework can be described as follows:

Figure 4. Theoretical Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The stages in this study and their information can be described as follows:

Figure 5. Research Methods

From the picture and explanation of the research methodology, the lighter colored box indicates the use of ISO 20000 in this study, while the darker colored box indicates the use of ITIL V3 2011. The ISO 20000 will be used in several processes, including the following:

1. Method for determining the scope of discussion of IT service management.
2. Processes identification that is in accordance with the problems of IT services at PT XYZ.
3. As a standard that must be used entirely, because PT XYZ does not have a business strategy document.
4. As a basis for mapping Service Level Management processes at ISO 20000 to ITIL V3 2011.

The use of ITIL V3 2011 in this study is as follows:

1. As a result of mapping from ISO 20000, the same process is also called Service Level Management.
2. As a guideline for determining the metrics that will be used in the service level agreement.
3. As a guideline or guide for creating or designing service level agreements.

IV. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The discussion of this research starts with listing the IT services, including Customer Facing Services (CFS) and Resource Facing Services (RFS). The stage for determining these IT services is by selecting company products and identifying services that support them. The product in question is product that is sold to customers or product used by internal users of the company. The next step is to list IT services that support the product.

The meaning of IT services at this stage is people, products, and processes. IT services are not software or hardware that is used, but rather the functionality of these services. IT services at PT XYZ are divided into 35 services which fall into 10 service categories. Service categories are divided based on the type of service, and sub-categories are divided by modules or details of services in the category. All services contained in PT XYZ are provided and managed by the IT division itself.

The next step is to mark Customer Facing Services (CFS) or Resources Facing Services (RFS). IT services in companies falls in the CFS category if customers or service users directly use the service. While IT services are categorized as RFS, if the customer or service user does not directly use the service and is not aware of the service. After identifying services that are included either in CFS and RFS, these services will be mapped with their service categories so that relationships between services in one service category can be seen. Some of the identified and mapped services are as follows:

Table 2. IT Service Identification and Mapping Results

No	IT Services Category	Layanan TI	CFS	RFS	Resources
1	Application Service	ABC Loyalty Program Application Service	X		
2		Timesheet Application Service	X		
3		ABC Database Backup Service			X
4		Timesheet Backup Database Service			X
5		ABC Database Service		X	
6		Timesheet Database Service		X	
7		ABC Application Report Service	X		

Next will be mapped each IT service that has been identified with users who use the service. Users are categorized by divisions at PT XYZ. The selected divisions are divisions that use IT services significantly, some divisions such as Creative and Analytic use tools that are not provided or managed by the IT division. The selected divisions are the

Account Executive division, Human Resource, Finance, Call Center, and IT division. The RACI graph (Responsible, Accountable, Consulted, Informed) is used for mapping IT services and their users. The followings are the mapping results with RACI charts:

Table 3. List of IT Service Users

No	IT Service Category	TI Service	IT Service User Division				
			ACC	FIN	HRD	CC	IT
1	Applicatin Service	ABC Loyalty Program Application Service	R			R	R
2		Timesheet Application Service	R	R	I	R	R
3		ABC Database Backup Service					R
4		Timesheet Backup Database Service					R
5		ABC Database Service					R
6		Timesheet Database Service					R
7		ABC Application Report Service	R			I	R

Survey of IT service problems is tailored to the services used by users, so users can know in detail what the problem is with each service. Surveys are carried out using two variables, namely impacts and tendency, where impact is the failure of a service that affects the ongoing business process. The impact here is defined as a failure that has happened for one year, while tendency is described as the frequency of service failure for one year.

Each variable is divided into three categories: High (H), Medium (M), and Low (L). High for impact is given a value of 3, meaning the failure that has ever occurred resulting in the service being down, the application cannot be accessed, or the loss of important data. Medium for impact is given a value of 2, meaning the failure that has ever occurred is significant enough, but does not disturb the availability of existing services. Low for impact is given a value of 1 in the sense that the failure occurs does not have a significant impact on service. As for the tendency of High is given a value of 3 in the sense that the frequency of events is more than 10 times a year (> 10). Medium for tendencies is given a value of 2, which means the frequency of events is between 3 and 10 times a year (3-10). Low for tendencies is given a value of 1, which means the frequency of occurrence is less than 3 times a year (<3). The following are the results of the survey on IT service problems:

Table 4. Survey Results on IT Service Problems

No	IT Service	Average		Result	
		D	K	D	K
1	ABC Loyalty Program Application Service	3.00	2.33	H	M
2	Timesheet Application Service	1.00	1.20	L	L
3	ABC Database Backup Service	1.00	1.00	L	L
4	Timesheet Backup Database Service	1.00	1.00	L	L
5	ABC Database Service	3.00	1.00	H	L
6	Timesheet Database Service	1.00	1.00	L	L
7	ABC Application Report Service	2.33	2.00	M	M

Of the 35 identified services, only two service level agreements were chosen to be made, this is because the tendency level is worth 2 or Medium and the service is that is directly used by users (Customer Facing Services). The reason for choosing CFS category services is because the level agreement that will be made is a service level agreement, if RFS is chosen, the level agreement made is an operational level agreement that is more internal and only used within the IT division.

Service level agreements are important because a service level agreement will ensure that the IT services provided are well-provided and measurable with the targets to be achieved. So if an IT service fails or is down, this is merely not a big problem to the management part. Failed services will be measured on how long the service is down and how long it takes to complete the service so that the service is active again based on the agreement to determine the target for each of the prioritized IT service. Services that will be a priority for determining targets are services that have high impact and tendency value based on the results of IT service problem surveys, namely the ABC Loyalty Program application service and Email services.

To determine the service level agreement target for ABC Loyalty Program and Email service application services, a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) is conducted that addresses technical issues related to service time, service availability, service reliability, customer support, and service performance. The specified target has been discussed and will be reported to the board of directors to be an evaluation material that will be applied to PT XYZ in the form of a service level agreement document. Service time is defined in the number of days in one week and one year. Service time must also include maintenance time and total maintenance days in one year. From the results of the discussion, the service time section consists of four metrics, namely the service time itself where

customers can expect services to be available, the total days of service available, the total time to do maintenance, and the total day of maintenance.

The metrics to be measured for the service availability section that has been agreed upon and in accordance with the definition of ITIL V3 2011 are total time between failures; which means the total of time between failures, total time to repair; which is the total time to improve service, down time; which is the number of down hours within one year, the downs number; meaning the down frequencies for one year, the average down time that occurred for one year, and the percentage of service availability.

The metrics on the reliability of services that have been agreed upon and in accordance with ITIL V3 2011 are, mean time between failures, which is the average time between failures that occur within one year, number of transactions on services, time of transactions on services, constants e , results from calculating one divided with MTBF, and service reliability percentage. Calculation of service reliability is adjusted to the circumstances of the company and in accordance with Curtis M. White's theory.

Metrics on customer support for a service that has been agreed upon and in accordance with the definition of ITIL V3 2011 are response times; which is the time needed by the service to respond to requests, time of resolution; which is the time needed from the detection stage to the service has been repaired, the total demand entry, total calls that were not picked-up, total telephone extensions that were always available for services, and percentage of customer support performance.

The metrics on service performance that has been agreed upon and in accordance with the definition of ITIL V3 2011 are total active users, response time needed by services, total users accessing services simultaneously, total transactions in one day, and service performance percentages. The measures defined above function to assess whether the part mentioned is in accordance with the target or not, so that further decisions can be taken to determine the next step. Not all parts defined by ITIL V3 2011 can be targeted, because there are several parts that cannot be measured or already exist based on the current condition of the company.

Based on the ISO 20000 process, it can be adjusted to the Plan-Do-Check-Act method in the service level management (SLM) process. These methods can be used to standardize service level management processes in accordance with ISO 20000. The methods that are in accordance with the FGD results are as follows:

1. *Plan*

- a) All services provided, including the target level of service and the appropriate load characteristics, must be agreed upon by various parties and there is a record of the agreement. The person responsible for this process is the IT Operation Manager.

2. *Do*

- a) Each service provided must be determined, agreed upon and documented in one or more

service level agreement agreements (SLAs). The person responsible for this process is the IT Operation Manager.

- b) Service level agreement (SLA), together with service agreement support, supplier contracts, and appropriate procedures, must be agreed upon by all relevant parties and there is a record of the agreement. The person in charge of this process is the IT Project Manager.

3. *Check*

- a) Service level agreements (SLAs) must be under the control of the change management process. The person in charge of this process is the IT Project Manager.
- b) Service level agreements (SLAs) must be maintained by related parties by periodically reviewing those service level agreements. Maintenance of this service level agreement is made to ensure that the service level agreements are always up to date and remain valid from time to time. The person responsible for this process is the IT Operation Manager.

4. *Act*

- a) Service levels must be monitored and reported based on the targets set, by displaying information both current information and current information trends. Corrective actions identified during this process must be recorded and used as input on planning to improve services. The person responsible for this process is the IT Operation Manager.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions in this study are as follows:

1. The problem that occurs in PT XYZ lies in the absence of service level agreements and the absence of a formal IT service management process.
2. The result of IT service categorization at PT XYZ is they have 35 IT services which are divided into three types of services, namely Customer Facing Services, Resources Facing Services and Resources.
3. IT services are divided into several users who use these services. Five divisions were identified, which plays a significant role in IT services, namely the Account division, the Human Resource division, the Finance division, the Call Center division, and the IT division itself.
4. Survey of problems in IT services is divided into 2 variables, namely Impact; which is defined as the failure of a service that influences ongoing business processes, and Trend; defined as the frequency of service failures.
5. Based on the survey results of IT service problems, there were seven services that have a high value impact (value of 3). Of these seven, two services were selected based on the level of trends that have

occurred. These two services are ABC Loyalty Program services and email services.

6. Problem solving was done using the ISO 20000 standard considering that ISO 20000 has a Service Level Management process and the 2011 ITIL V3 framework to find out what should be done to create a service level agreement.
 7. The result of ISO 20000 and ITIL V3 2011 mapping is one to one. The ISO 20000 process is Service Level Management and the ITIL V3 2011 process is Service Level Management.
 8. The results of discussions with several colleagues at PT XYZ who have roles and responsibilities for service level agreements are targets set for the two selected services.
 9. The metrics determination on service level agreements at PT XYZ is only based on the operational metrics and tolerance theory by Randy A. Steinberg. More studies are expected, focusing more on the overall metric to achieve metrics for management decisions
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VI. REFERENCES

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